

A

B

Supplementary figure 1. EGFP+ myeloid cells localization in the brain after HI
Representative tile-scanned confocal images of brain sections after HI. EGFP+ myeloid cells markedly infiltrate the striatum 1 day (**A**) but not 7 day (**B**) after HI. n=4.